

Path coefficient studies for Quantitative Traits in Greengram [*Vigna radiata* (L.)Wilczek] Genotypes

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Abstract

Mungbean is one of the leading pulse crops in india.it is one of the important food legumes of many tropical and subtropical parts of the world. Path studies give an idea about the contribution of different characters to seed yield. The path analysis in respect of various desirable characters in for 40 greengram germplasm for 10 quantitative traits *viz.*, days to 50 per cent flowering, number of branches per plant, plant height (cm), number of clusters per plant, number of pods per plant, number of pods per cluster, number of seed per pod, pod length (cm), single plant yield (g) and hundred seed weight (g) were evaluated at two different centers *viz.*, Agricultural College and Research Institute, TNAU, Madurai and Agricultural Research Station, TNAU, Vaigai Dam. It will help in isolating promising lines for hybridization programmes and to explore yield potential and quality of mung bean.

Key words: Path analysis, Germplasm, Mungbean, Quantitative characters

Introduction

Pluses are extensively grown in tropical regions of the world as a major protein rich crop bringing considerable improvement in human diet. It is one of the important food legumes of many tropical and subtropical parts of the world. India is considered as its land of origin (Lawn and Ahn, 2002). It is grown almost all over the country and has the potential to make up the gap of protein shortage. But yield per acre in the country is still marginal. Mungbean is a short duration grain legume crops with wide adaptability and deep root system, low input requirements, and suitable for crop rotations, intercropping, relay cropping and as catch crop (Devendra payasi *et al.*, 2010). Path studies give an idea about the contribution of different characters to seed yield (VAndana and Dubey, 1993). Direct and indirect effects of economically useful traits with seed yield were also investigated. Genetic diversity analyses can be performed on both qualitative and quantitative data

or on a combination of both. Path analysis will establish the extent of association between yield and yield components and bring out relative importance of their direct and indirect effects and these give a clear understanding of their association with yield.

Path coefficient analysis permits the separation of the direct effects from the indirect effects through other related characters by partitioning the genotypic correlation coefficients, providing a clear picture of the characters that can be relied upon in a selection programme for improvement of grain yield. So far very limited work has been done for the improvement of barnyard millet crop. Therefore, an attempt has been made in the present study to estimate their direct and indirect contributions through path coefficient analysis.

Material and Methods

The present investigation was carried out in 40 mungbean genotypes. The trials were laid out in randomized block design with three replications at three different environments *viz.*, Agricultural College and Research Institute (ACRI), TNAU, Madurai (E1), Agricultural Research Station, TNAU, Vaigai Dam (E2) and ACRI, TNAU, Madurai (E3). In this study, genotypic correlation for 10 quantitative traits *viz.*, days to 50 per cent flowering, number of branches per plant, plant height, number of clusters per plant, number of pods per plant, number of pods per cluster, number of seed per pod, pod length, single plant yield and hundred seed weight were analyzed. Path coefficient analysis was carried out as suggested by Dewey and Lu (1959).

Results and discussion

Path coefficient analysis would be useful, as it permits the separation of direct effect from indirect effects through other related traits by partitioning the genotypic correlation coefficient (Dewey and Lu, 1959). A character like seed yield is dependent on several mutually associated component characters and change in any one of the components is likely to affect the whole network of cause-and-effect relationship. This in turn might affect the true association of component characters, both in magnitude and direction and tend to vitiate association of yield and yield components. Hence it is necessary to partition the phenotypic correlations of component characters into direct and indirect effects (Biradar *et al.*, 2007).

In the present study, direct and indirect effects of yield contributing components on seed yield were worked out.

Table 1. Direct and indirect effects of different yield attributing traits with grain yield in AC &RI, Madurai, Kharif 2012 (E1)

Trait	Days to fifty percent flowering	Number of branches per plant	Plant height	Number of clusters per plant	Number of pods per plant	Number of pods per cluster	Number of seeds per pod	Pod length	Hundred Seed weight
Days to fifty percent flowering	0.366	-0.482	0.398	-0.239	-0.014	-0.015	-0.123	-0.033	-0.051
Number of branches per plant	0.274	-0.646	0.493	0.209	-0.045	-0.003	-0.262	-0.040	0.080
Plant height	0.241	-0.525	0.606	0.104	-0.082	-0.005	-0.270	-0.042	0.095
Number of clusters per plant	-0.058	-0.090	0.042	1.507	-0.180	-0.023	-0.408	0.121	0.118
Number of pods per plant	0.013	-0.071	0.124	0.670	-0.404	-0.013	0.008	-0.013	0.208
Number of pods per cluster	0.062	-0.022	0.032	0.373	-0.060	-0.091	-0.193	0.041	0.011
Number of seeds per pod	0.066	-0.247	0.240	0.898	0.005	-0.026	-0.684	0.170	0.117
Pod length	-0.065	0.140	-0.138	0.996	0.029	-0.020	-0.632	0.184	0.081
Hundred Seed weight	-0.044	-0.124	0.138	0.426	-0.200	-0.002	-0.192	0.036	0.419

Residual effect: 0.471

Table 2. Direct and indirect effects of different yield attributing traits with grain yield in ARS, Vaigai Dam, Kharif 2012 (E2)

Trait	Days to fifty percent flowering	Number of branches per plant	Plant height	Number of clusters per plant	Number of pods per plant	Number of pods per cluster	Number of seeds per pod	Pod length	Hundred Seed weight
Days to fifty percent flowering	0.039	-0.020	0.056	0.013	0.330	0.001	-0.050	-0.086	-0.084
Number of branches per plant	0.009	-0.085	0.102	-0.013	0.172	0.003	-0.095	-0.093	-0.003
Plant height	0.015	-0.061	0.143	-0.011	0.015	-0.009	-0.130	-0.072	0.037
Number of clusters per plant	0.003	0.007	-0.010	0.152	0.469	0.006	-0.244	0.054	-0.137
Number of pods per plant	0.012	-0.014	0.002	0.066	1.072	0.055	-0.179	-0.036	-0.214
Number of pods per cluster	0.001	-0.002	-0.013	0.010	0.648	0.091	-0.164	-0.066	-0.059
Number of seeds per pod	0.003	-0.014	0.031	0.062	0.320	0.025	-0.600	0.090	-0.005
Pod length	-0.013	0.030	-0.039	0.031	-0.146	-0.023	-0.204	0.264	-0.013
Hundred Seed weight	0.010	-0.001	-0.017	0.066	0.725	0.017	-0.009	0.011	-0.316

Residual effect: 0.475

Table 3. Direct and indirect effects of different yield attributing traits with grain yield in AC & RI, Madurai, *Rabi* 2012 (E3)

Trait	Days to fifty percent flowering	Number of branches per plant	Plant height	Number of clusters per plant	Number of pods per plant	Number of pods per cluster	Number of seeds per pod	Pod length	Hundred Seed weight
Days to fifty percent flowering	-0.288	1.328	-0.702	0.113	0.124	0.008	-0.574	0.007	-0.068
Number of branches per plant	-0.118	3.248	-0.734	-0.859	0.076	0.029	-1.697	0.045	0.107
Plant height	-0.180	2.123	-1.124	0.581	0.013	0.013	-1.189	-0.002	0.021
Number of clusters per plant	-0.007	-0.567	-0.132	4.926	-0.169	0.068	-3.195	-0.031	-0.473
Number of pods per plant	0.063	-0.437	0.025	1.464	-0.568	0.103	-1.292	-0.097	0.957
Number of pods per cluster	-0.005	0.221	-0.035	0.795	-0.138	0.422	-1.429	-0.024	0.505
Number of seeds per pod	-0.034	1.153	-0.279	3.293	-0.153	0.126	-4.781	0.004	0.803
Pod length	-0.005	0.339	0.005	-0.357	0.128	-0.024	-0.045	0.429	-0.594
Hundred Seed weight	0.007	0.131	-0.009	-0.877	-0.205	0.080	-1.446	-0.096	2.656

Residual effect: 1.04

Direct effect

The dependent variable taken into consideration for path analysis was single plant yield. Among the ten traits analyzed, five traits showed positive direct effect and the remaining four characters showed negative direct effect on single plant yield. The highest positive direct effect was registered by number of clusters per plant (1.507) followed by plant height (0.606), hundred seed weight (0.419), days to 50% flowering (0.366) and pod length (0.184). Negative direct effect was recorded through number of seeds per pod (-0.684) followed by number of branches per plant (-0.646), number of pods per plant (-0.404) and number of pods per cluster (-0.091) in **E1 AC & RI, Madurai, Kharif**.

Among ten quantitative characters studied, six characters showed positive direct effects and the remaining four characters showed negative direct effects on single plant yield. The highest positive direct effect was registered by number of pods per plant (1.072) followed by pod length (0.264), number of clusters per plant (0.152), plant height (0.143), number of pods per cluster (0.091) and days to 50% flowering (0.039). Negative direct effect was recorded through number of seeds per pod (-0.600) followed by hundred seed weight (-0.316) and number of branches per plant (-0.085) in **E2 AC & RI, Madurai, Kharif**.

The dependent variable taken into consideration for path analysis was single plant yield. Among the ten traits analyzed, five traits showed positive direct effect and the remaining four characters showed negative direct effect on single plant yield. The highest positive direct effect was registered by number of clusters per plant (4.926) followed by number of seeds per pod (4.781), number of branches per plant (3.248), hundred seed weight (2.656), number of pods per cluster (0.568) and pod length (0.429). Negative direct effect was recorded through followed by plant height (-1.124), number of pods per plant (-0.422) and days to 50% flowering (-0.288) in **E3 AC & RI, Madurai, Rabi**

The highest positive direct effect registered by number of clusters per plant and plant height in AC & RI, Madurai, *Kharif* season (E1 location) and ARS, Vaigai Dam, *Kharif* season (E2 location). This was in accordance with the earlier findings Chauhan *et al.* (2007), Luman Hakim (2008), Kousar Makeen *et al.* (2009) and Suresh *et al.*, (2010) in greengram. The characters exerting direct effect on seed yield were number of pods per plant, 100 seed weight and days to maturity in Kalpande *et al.* (1998)

Indirect effects:

The other characters which had indirect positive effect on single plant yield was number of branches per plant, number of seeds per pod, number of pods per plant at AC & RI, Madurai, *kharif* season (E1 location), number of seeds per pod, hundred seed weight at ARS, Vaigai Dam, *Kharif* season (E2), number of seeds per pod, days to fifty percent flowering in AC & RI, Madurai,

rabi season (E3). Pod length had high positive direct effect in all the locations. Similar results were reported by Ved Prakash *et al.* (2007). The characters exerting direct effect on seed yield were number of pods per plant, 100 seed weight and days to maturity in Kalpande *et al.* (1998). It was concluded that characters with positive effects should be significantly considered in selection criteria for yield improvement in mungbean breeding programs.

Conclusion:

The seed yield is an important parameter among all the morphological as well as yield traits. That selection for days to 50% flowering, hundred seed weight, number of clusters per plant, number of pods per plant and number of branches per plant should be given importance to increase the seed yield in greengram.

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